
Analysis of Performances of kNN and Random Forest

A Data Management Plan created using dmponline

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Template: DCC Template

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Project abstract:

This project aims to evaluate the performances of different settings for the k-nearest-neighbor algorithm and the random forest algorithm on two publicly available datasets of different sizes. With this project we want to show the differences between a small dataset with only 100 rows and a medium sized dataset with 10.000 rows. Both datasets (Zoo and Phishing Websites) are already preprocessed and do not contain any missing values

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Data Collection

What data will you collect or create?

All data is stored as CSV files, as this type of files does not produce any large overhead and are easily archivable, as such files only contain text, which is separated with commas. This is therefore the best choice going forward, as such files allow other researchers to easily rerun the complete experiment.

Also CSV files are state of the art in most research areas. Changes in this files can easily be tracked.

Input Data

As Input data this project accesses two external CSV datasets. Both datasets have been downloaded and saved along with the source code in the folders phishing/input/ and zoo/input/ respectively.

The files are made available at the following Locations:

1. Zoo: Dua, D. and Graff, C. (2019). UCI Machine Learning Repository [<http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml>]. Irvine, CA: University of California, School of Information and Computer Science.
Available at: <https://www.openml.org/d/62> (Accessed on 14 April 2021)
Download Directlink: https://www.openml.org/data/get_csv/52352/openml_phpZNNasq
File Download Location: input/zoo.csv
File Size: 11 KB
2. PhishingWebsites: Dua, D. and Graff, C. (2019). UCI Machine Learning Repository [<http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml>]. Irvine, CA: University of California, School of Information and Computer Science.
Available at: <https://www.openml.org/d/4534> (Accessed on 14 April 2021)
Download Directlink: https://www.openml.org/data/get_csv/1798106/phpV5QYya
File Download Location: input/phishing.csv
File Size: 782KB

Produced Data

The produced data is stored in the path results/.

There are four result files, which contain the accuracy, precision, recall and fbeta values for each run test. In our case this are for both datasets kNN classification and random forest classification.

These files are named:

- phishing_forest.csv
File Size: 2KB
- phishing_kNN.csv
File Size: 18KB
- zoo_forest.csv
File Size: 2 KB

- zoo_kNN.csv
File Size: 15 KB

Furthermore there are 10 plots generated for the output, which are stored in the evaluation folder. These plots are named in the following format:
{algorithm}_{dataset}_{additionalInformation}.png

This results into the following files:

- phishing_forest.png
File Size: 237 KB
- phishing_forest_metrics.png
File Size: 372 KB
- phishing_kNN_best_accuracy.png
File Size: 290 KB
- phishing_kNN_distance_euclidean.png
File Size: 491 KB
- phishing_kNN_uniform_euclidean.png
File Size: 283 KB
- zoo_forest.png
File Size: 234 KB
- zoo_forest_metrics.png
File Size: 406 KB
- zoo_kNN_best_accuracy.png
File Size: 303 KB
- zoo_kNN_distance_euclidean.png
File Size: 434 KB
- zoo_kNN_uniform_euclidean.png
File Size: 303 KB

How will the data be collected or created?

The input data will be downloaded via the Webinterface of <https://www.openml.org> and then stored in the input folder renamed as zoo.csv and phishing.csv.

Folder Structure

The Folder Structure for this project will aim to be simple and easy to use, therefore we are only creating 4 folders, which are all on the root level.

- Input
The folder "input/" contains the two renamed input files. From this two input files (phishing.csv, zoo.csv), we will generate new Trainings and Test splits, which will be named phishing.lrn.csv, phishing.tes.csv and zoo.lrn.csv and zoo.tes.csv. In this folder there is an additional folder "Metadata/" in which the descriptions for the Phishing dataset can be found.
- Results
The folder "results/" contains our four different result files, which contain results for each dataset and each method. These files will be named {dataset}_{method}.csv for all files, which corresponds to:
 - phishing_forest.csv
 - phishing_kNN.csv
 - zoo_forest.csv
 - zoo_kNN.csv

- Evaluation
The folder "evaluation/" contains ten different plots, which show the evaluation of the data. These plots show graphically how the accuracy, precision and recall are evolving with different settings.
These plots are named in the following format:
{algorithm}_{dataset}_{additionalInformation}.png
- Scripts
The folder "scripts/" contains the three different scripts, those files have the format "{datasetUsedFor}{Predictor|Plotter}.py, which corresponds to the following files:
 - PhishingPredictor.csv
 - ZooPredictor.csv
 - Plotter.csv

Versioning

To version the different versions of our data, git is used, this repository will handle all different versions of our files, so that we can track changes and if needed, rollback to earlier releases. The repository will be available at:
<https://github.com/MoritzStaudinger/classificationperformancer>

Quality Assurance Processes

There are no additional quality assurance processes for the Data Management executed, but Tobias Hajszan and Moritz Staudinger have made the repository publicly available and also allow issues to be open, so that they can be made aware of possible problems with the data.

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

The metadata for both datasets is available at openml.org.

Zoo Dataset

Available under CC-BY license at [OpenML Zoo](https://openml.org/dataset/1). This Dataset was published by Richard S. Forsyth on 15.5.1990. The metadata, with descriptions on all features and animals is directly available at the before mentioned link. There is a description available for all the columns on the website, and all columns contain easily understandable information.

As for example, if the column is named fur, this corresponds to the question: "Does this animal have hair?", which can be answered with yes or no.

Phishing Dataset

This dataset is also available under CC-BY license at [OpenML Phishing](https://openml.org/dataset/10). The dataset was first being uploaded to openML on 16.02.2016. It has been used for various research papers before, which dates back until 2012. As many of the features are not speaking as they have been intensely preprocessed, the Authors Rami Mustafa A Mohammad et al. have produced metadata, which is available at [Metadata \(DOCX\)](#). This description can be found also under /input/Metadata/Phishing Websites Features.docx .

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

There is no sensitive information contained in the data, as the zoo dataset does not contain any sensitive information and the phishing dataset is only provided in an anonymized form. Therefore, it is not necessary to manage ethical issues, as no dataset contains data, which could lead to ethical issues.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

The Zoo Dataset was created by Richard S. Forsyth and is provided by the University of California. It has been made available under the CC-BY license.

Similar to this, the phishing dataset was created by Rami Mustafa A Mohammad et al. and is provided by the University of California as well. As all datasets at openml.org it is available under the CC-BY license.

The newly created data is owned by Technische Universität Wien, as it was a research project during a course, and has been created by Tobias Hajszan and Moritz Staudinger.

All newly created Data will also be made available under CC-BY and be made available immediately per April 19th 2021.

The code will be made available at

<https://github.com/MoritzStaudinger/classificationperformancer> under the MIT License, without an Embargo period.

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

During Research the data will be stored on Github.com. As both datasets are smaller than 1MB it is not necessary to use any additional services to store and host the datasets.

The Github repository will be regularly backed up by Github and also additionally in the process of normal Computer backup guidelines every week on an additional server with all other necessary data from the work computer.

Furthermore will the data be also kept on the internal GitLab Server git.overheat.me, as a second Git instance, to have another reliable backup.

In the case of an incident the data can be either regained by cloning the repository newly from Github/GitLab, or in a worst case scenario, in which the Repository on Github and Gitlab have been deleted, as well as all local copies of the data are also ruined, by using the backups from TU Wien, with the changes from last week.

To sum this up, the data is stored on multiple GitLab/Github servers, and additionally on our Work Computers. In case of an incident, the data can be recreated by using one of the still available data sources.

How will you manage access and security?

Access to the data will be made available via git. All researchers on this dataset, will gain a developer role on this project and as soon as the project has finished, the data will be made publicly available. This can only be done with an account at Github.com and a secure password or SSH key, which is approved by Github.com.

With the restricted access on the research, and also two private repositories, it should not be possible for unallowed people to access the data.

Furthermore all working devices are encrypted to ensure, that if a device is lost or stolen, it is not possible to access the data easily.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

The results that should be retained to reprocess the experiment are the four CSV files in the result folder. These files are:

- phishing_forest.csv
- phishing_kNN.csv
- zoo_forest.csv
- zoo_kNN.csv

With these files it is possible to reconstruct the original output of the experiment and evaluate if the experiment has been done correctly.

As all the data is open source, it is not necessary to remove any data from the project, but it is not necessary to keep all created plots, as these plots are easily creatable, as long as the CSV files have been kept.

The beforementioned files will be made available at Zenodo and the Source Code will be made available at Github.

For the foreseeable future, it would be great to keep the results and implementations, so that we can evaluate other algorithms on the same datasets so that our results are comparable.

As the data is not the part of a paper and is not planned to be handed in as a Proposal at a conference, the data will be stored for one year, as the sklearn library is continuously evolving and this could lead to backwards incompatibility.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

The Source code and the produced results of the experiment will be made available at [Zenodo](#) and the source code will additionally be made available at Github.

There are no additional costs for Zenodo and Github for the data repositories.

The datasets are available under the following links:

Results: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4699026>

Code: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4699023>

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

The data and the Source code will be made openly available at Zenodo and Github. There will additionally be keywords used, so that potential interested users can find the data easily.

All the data is being shared under the CC-BY license, as both datasets have been also been made available under CC-BY. The source code is available under the MIT license. The sharing will be made available via the Github and also the Zenodo repository.

The data will be made available on 19. April 2021 on Zenodo, and both the data as well as the source code will be available under a digital object identifier.

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

There is no need for any restrictions on data sharing required.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

The responsibility for the data management lies by Moritz Staudinger (moritz.staudinger@tuwien.ac.at) On each change of the project in the future, the data management plan will be reviewed and revised by him.

As this project has only be done at TU Wien for a single research project, it is not necessary to split the responsibilities of the data management with any other institutions or colleagues.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

There are no additional resources be required to deliver this data management plan.